

Sustainable eThics **R**eviews of digital heAlth Technology dEsiGn In sub saharan afriCa (**STRATEGIC**)

Deliverable No. 2.2

Ethics of Digital Health Technology Design handbook

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E D C T P

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Abstract	This deliverable reviews key ethical issues relating to digital health technologies in sub-Saharan Africa, in the context of clinical practice and clinical trials, whilst identifying challenges and implications for the ethics review infrastructure. Recommendations were set out for trustworthy and culturally-sensitive digital health technologies, which can effectively support the STRATEGIC project's objective of fostering the ethics and regulatory capacity in SSA.
Key Words	Ethics, digital health, Africa, clinical trials, clinical practice

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List of acronyms/abbreviations

Abbreviation	Explanation
LUMSA	Libera Università Maria Ss. Assunta
GHS	Ghana Health Service
UoN	University of Nottingham
LETS	Université de Yaoundé
UEM	Universidade Eduardo Mondlane
SSA	Sub-Saharan Africa
DHTs	Digital Health Technologies
STRATEGIC	Sustainable eThics Reviews of digital health Technology dEsiGn In subsaharan afriCa
ICT	Information and Communication Technology
AI	Artificial Intelligence
EDCTP	European & Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership
WHO	World Health Organization
ML	Machine Learning
mHealth	Mobile Health
WFP	World Food Program
CIOMS	Council of International Organizations of Medical Sciences
DCTs	Decentralised Clinical Trials

EDC	Electronic Data Capture
REDCap	Research Electronic Data Capture
ePRO	Electronic Patient-Reported Outcome
NECs	National Ethics Committees
NRAs	National Research Authorities
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
WMA	World Medical Association

List of acronyms/abbreviations

Executive Summary

The deliverable critically discusses findings stemming from a narrative literature review of ethical issues relating to digital health technologies in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). This review checked which digital health technologies are used in SSA, in the context of clinical trials and clinical practice, highlighting the ethical issues they entail. Based on literature evidence, the focus was set on a selection of digital health technologies used in SSA to analyse gaps and needs from an ethics perspective, along with identifying challenges and implications for the ethics review infrastructure: findings highlight that SSA accounts for the highest burden of disease in the world and the greatest scarcity of healthcare workers. If, on one hand, digital health technologies can improve healthcare in the region by increasing access to care and enhancing the efficiency of the healthcare system (traditional healthcare systems are usually underdeveloped, understaffed, or not accessible at all); on the other, SSA is experiencing an expansion of digital health services, but the use of these technologies remains heterogeneous. Among the key ethical challenges devised, several ones are common to clinical practice and clinical trials settings. Furthermore, we identified some ethical challenges pertaining to the use of digital health technologies in clinical trials, notably in the context of decentralised trials. Drawing on these findings, preliminary recommendations were set out suggesting context-specific interventions to foster fair access of digital health technologies; care and respect for human dignity requirements; trustworthy technologies and forms of collaboration based on community engagement and involving stakeholders to co-design culturally-sensitive digital health solutions and informed consent; strengthening capacity for reviewing research protocols with digital health tools. Considering the ethical issues highlighted in this deliverable will be of paramount importance to effectively support the STRATEGIC project's objective of enhancing the ethics and regulatory capacity in SSA and to ensure the design and deployment of responsible digital health technologies for clinical research and practice.

1. Methodology

This deliverable aims to explore ethical issues relating to digital health technologies (DHTs) in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA). In particular, its central objective is to check whether and which digital health technologies are used for clinical trials and clinical practice. Findings collection includes a narrative literature review conducted in WP2 (Task 2.2), which encompasses the collection and analysis of institutional documents dealing with ethics surrounding the use of digital health technologies in SSA. Evidence on the ethical issues these technologies raise was collected and described – also relying on key findings from Focus Group discussions carried out in Task 2.3 - to identify the challenges and implications for the SSA ethics review infrastructure regarding a literature-based selection of DHTs used in SSA. Research outcomes were critically appraised, in order to draw up preliminary recommendations for an ethical design of digital health technologies, tailored to African values and needs, which will be refined and further developed in WP4.

Type of Study:

Review and analysis of literature and institutional documents dealing with ethics of digital health technologies in sub-Saharan Africa.

Task Leader:

LUMSA

Contributing Partners:

GHS, UoN

Description of specific objectives

1. To analyse already existing findings of Tasks 2.1 and 2.3 related to Task 2.2 general objective.
2. To carry out a narrative literature review and analyse evidence concerning ethical and legal issues relating to digital health technologies in sub-Saharan Africa.
3. To check which digital health technologies are used in SSA, in the context of clinical trials and clinical practice, highlighting the ethical issues they entail.
4. Based on literature evidence, to focus on a selection of digital health technologies used in SSA to analyse gaps and needs from an ethics perspective.
5. To analyse institutional documents issued by international and African organizations tackling ethics issues relating to the use of digital health technologies within clinical trials and clinical practice.
6. To identify challenges and implications for the ethics review infrastructure based on literature evidence and institutional documents' analysis.
7. To draft a first summary of the results concerning an ethical use of digital health technologies in SSA.
8. To discuss results during online workshops with African and International experts in bioethics and ethics in digital technologies.
9. To draft a final report, including recommendations, taking into account insights from the workshops with African and International experts.
10. To prepare an ethics of digital health technology design handbook for the implementation of D2.2 based on task 2.2 final report and key findings provided by GHS from tasks 2.1 literature review and 2.3 Focus Group discussions on African ethical principles and values for digital health tech design.

Sources

Inclusion criteria

Literature

- Findings from task 2.1
- Scientific literature:
PubMed: <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pubmed/>;
Scopus: <https://www.scopus.com/search/form.uri?display=basic>
Google Scholar: www.scholar.google.com
Encyclopedia of Global Bioethics: <https://link.springer.com/referencework/10.1007/978-3-319-09483-0>
Springer Link: <https://link.springer.com/>
Sage Journal: <https://journals.sagepub.com/>
Wiley Interscience: <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/>
African Journal of Bioethics: <https://www.africanjournalofbioethics.org/>

Years considered: 2014 to present

Geographical area considered: sub-Saharan Africa (list of countries: https://international-partnerships.ec.europa.eu/countries/sub-saharan-africa_en#countries-in-the-region)

Language: English

Institutional documents

- Documents, recommendations of institutions at International and African levels
- Institutional websites:
 - <https://au.int/en>
 - <https://www.afro.who.int/>
 - https://www.who.int/health-topics/ethics-and-health#tab=tab_1
 - <https://www.who.int/groups/global-summit-of-national-bioethics-committees>
 - <https://www.unesco.org/en/ethics-science-technology/ibc>
 - <https://www.wma.net/>
 - <https://cioms.ch/bioethics/>
 - [COPAB – Qu’ils aient la vie en abondance \(copab-ankh.org\)](http://COPAB – Qu’ils aient la vie en abondance (copab-ankh.org))

- [African Consortium of Bioethicists \(ACB\) \(sun.ac.za\)](http://sun.ac.za)
- <https://ahri.gov.et/pan-africa-bioethics-initiatives-pabin/>
- <https://africabioethicsnetwork.org/index.php/about-us>

Keywords

Population

- Woman/women+SSA/sub-Saharan Africa/SSA country name
- Man/men+SSA/sub-Saharan Africa/SSA country name
- Child/children/minor+SSA/sub-Saharan Africa/SSA country name
- Elderly/old people+SSA/sub-Saharan Africa/SSA country name
- Disability/disabled+SSA/sub-Saharan Africa/SSA country name
- Ethnic-cultural diversity+SSA/sub-Saharan Africa/SSA country name

Topics

- Ethics and Digital health/Digital technologies and clinical research/clinical trials/health research/clinical practice/medical practice
- Ethics and mobile health/mHealth and clinical research/clinical trials/health research/clinical practice/medical practice
- Ethics and ICT and clinical research/clinical trials/health research/clinical practice/medical practice
- Ethics and Artificial Intelligence/AI and clinical research/clinical trials/health research/clinical practice/medical practice
- Ethics and Autonomy/Informed Consent and Digital health/Digital technologies and clinical research/clinical trials/health research/clinical practice/medical practice
- Ethics and Justice and Digital health/Digital technologies and clinical research/clinical trials/health research/clinical practice/medical practice
- Ethics and Privacy/Data Protection and Digital health/Digital technologies and clinical research/clinical trials/health research/clinical practice/medical practice

- Ethics and Security/Safety/Misuse and Digital health/Digital technologies and clinical research/clinical trials/health research/clinical practice/medical practice
- Ethics and Responsibility/Accountability/Transparency and Digital health/Digital technologies and clinical research/clinical trials/health research/clinical practice/medical practice

Exclusion criteria

Legal documents (regulations, recommendations, guidelines) issued by National Regulatory Authorities.

Analysis process

The search, selection and analysis process encompasses three steps:

- 1- One researcher will independently carry out the research following the inclusion and exclusion criteria.
- 2- A different researcher will screen and assess if the studies found are relevant and meet the inclusion criteria.
- 3- The team of researchers will analyse the main findings and include them in a final draft with recommendations.

Timeline

- May 2024 – July 2024: collection of literature and institutional documents
- August 2024 – September 2024: start of analysis of literature, institutional documents
- October 2024 – November 2024: completion of analysis and start of drafting of a preliminary summary of findings
- December 2024: completion of drafting of a preliminary summary of findings
- January 2025-March 2025: organizing two hybrid Workshops with African and International experts in bioethics and ethics of digital technologies. A first hybrid workshop with Prof. Jacques Simpore - Full Professor of Molecular Biology and Molecular Genetics, Université Joseph KI-ZERBO, Director of the Pietro Annigoni Biomolecular Research Center CERBA / LABIOGENE, and Member of the Pontifical Academy for Life, Vatican - was held on March 6th, 2025, at LUMSA University in Rome. A second hybrid workshop with Dr. Dafna Feinholz - Chief of Bioethics and Ethics of Science and Technology Section at UNESCO – was held on March 27th, 2025, at LUMSA University in Rome. STRATEGIC partners participated remotely in discussions with experts based on a set of key ethical questions devised and prepared before the workshops, to validate literature preliminary findings and tackle open challenges; revising first draft according to insights from the Workshops; refinement of literature review to include key aspects stemming

from discussion with African and International experts and elaboration of a final report of summary of findings

- April 2025-December 2025: preparing an ethics of digital health technology design handbook

Key ethical questions for Workshops with experts

- 1) According to your knowledge, are digital health technologies used in sub-Saharan Africa in clinical research and medical practice? If this is the case, which technologies are used and in which countries of this geographical area?
- 2) Are digital health technologies currently being used in sub-Saharan Africa to modernise clinical trials' processes by improving efficiency, accuracy and patient engagement?
- 3) In your opinion, what are the key ethical challenges and implications regarding the use of digital health technologies in sub-Saharan Africa? Are these technologies aligned with African cultural values?
- 4) Which possible stakeholders (for research activities and policy engagement) would you suggest engaging in and beyond sub-Saharan Africa?

Focus group discussions: Data Collection and Analysis

The focus group discussions are part of the review of ethics and legal infrastructure issues where African ethical principles and values were identified for digital health tech design. The exercise was meant to be a values elicitation process where common values and principles that could inform the design and evaluation of digital technologies for wide range of stakeholders are identified and prioritized.

Figure: Innovation life cycle

Nine focus group discussions were conducted with forty-nine participants from fifteen countries in Europe and Africa. Participants were identified from the European & Developing Countries Clinical Trials Partnership (EDCTP) funded projects - both completed and ongoing. This activity envisaged the

adoption of the innovation life cycle to guide engagement with participants and presented four questions alongside the four stages of the life cycle:

Ideation stage: What values and principles do you think should shape the ideation stage of the innovation lifecycle in Africa?

- General or unique African values and principles as well as cultural beliefs and practices
- What cultural norms, traditions and practices can or do influence ideation of Digital Health Technologies in Africa?
- What ethical concerns should be prioritised when designing ideating for health technologies in Africa?

Design and development stage: What values and principles should shape design and development of digital health technologies?

- This includes software and hardware, and for data collection, testing, validation

Deployment stage: What cultural beliefs and practices shape the use of digital health technologies for clinical trials and research?

- This includes making the technology public to users and its adoption in clinical settings and scaling

Governance of DHT: In your opinion, what systems/framework should be put in place to ensure that suppliers, developers and users/deployers consider the ethical and legal implications of these technologies?

- What is one key principle and or value you believe must be integrated into digital health technologies for clinical trials and research?
- How should data governance and sovereignty be handled to ensure that African researchers and participants benefit from digital health data?

The focus group discussions were recorded in Microsoft Teams, transcribed, and cleaned before thematic coding and analysis using MAXQDA (verbatim) and Nvivo 12 (cleaned). The data collected were analyzed using Thematic–Content Analysis which integrates inductive thematic analysis (Braun & Clarke, 2006) with deductive Content Analysis (Elo & Kyngäs, 2008). This approach is ideal for interdisciplinary inquiries requiring both emergent meanings and structured categorization (Fereday & Muir-Cochrane, 2006). The process occurred in two phases:

- Themes were generated openly from the data (both pure transcript and cleaned data) using inductive coding.
- Using deductive mapping, themes were categorized into three overarching dimensions aligned with research question: RQ1, RQ2, RQ3 and RQ4.

To enhance reliability, two independent coders analyzed the datasets from GHS and UoN. Intercoder agreement was assessed, and researcher reflexivity was maintained through memo-writing and positionality statements (Finlay, 2002). Reporting of findings adhered to some aspect of the COREQ checklist (Tong, Sainsbury, & Craig, 2007).

2. Digital health in sub-Saharan Africa: an overview

The World Health Organisation's (WHO) *Global Strategy on Digital Health 2020-2025*¹ emphasizes the key role of digital health technologies in clinical trials and clinical practice. Several countries in sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) are already reaching important achievements in the integration of digital health technologies (such as mHealth, electronic health records, telemedicine, cloud-based applications, artificial intelligence) into healthcare systems.

Over the past two decades, SSA has faced multiple health emergencies: between 2001 and 2022 the region reported about 1.800 public health emergencies, mainly emerging infectious diseases (Moyo et al., 2023). These are diseases that are new or resurgent diseases in the population including but not limited to cholera, meningitis, Ebola, measles, yellow fever, monkeypox, COVID-19 and malaria.

Against this backdrop, to provide a strong response to the burden these diseases place on African individuals and societies, an ecosystem of digital technology has come to the fore in SSA: from big data analytic tools used to improve Ebola surveillance- providing a timelier, and a more precise response to emergency outbreaks (Bempong et al., 2019), to mobile and web-based communication platforms, surveillance systems and data analysis tools for real-time decision making and evaluation of malaria interventions.

Indeed, there is an emerging ecosystem of digital health technologies (such as an open-source mobile digital platform for clinical trial data collection established in Kenya (Dam et al., 2017)) being developed in and for sub-Saharan Africa to expand clinical research, democratise and create solutions for health-related challenges.

As advancements in digital health technologies provide capabilities to transform clinical trials and clinical practice, their application in SSA offers unique opportunities as well as concerns. Literature findings highlight that by expanding the use of digital health technologies for clinical purposes, African health systems could become more efficient (Jousset et al., 2023).

In particular, digital health technologies refer to digital devices, systems and applications that facilitate digital health data generation, analysis and application in clinical trials and clinical practice. This includes systems for: collecting electronic patient records, remote patient recruitment and consent, real-time data monitoring and evidence generation, big data analytics, telemedicine and virtual consultations and clinical decision support systems. The use of these technologies, including artificial intelligence (AI) based technologies, raises new issues and requires a critical reassessment of established concerns. These include issues such as meaningful human control, safety, explainability, avoidance of biases and non discrimination, autonomy and informed consent, privacy and data security, equity and accessibility, accountability, liability and responsibility, and ethical use of big data (quality of data, privacy and data sharing). Many of these concerns are still emerging and there is no clear understanding of how exactly they will unfold or how to address them effectively. Questions of balancing the promised benefits of

¹ The WHO defines digital health as: "the field of knowledge and practice associated with the development and use of digital technologies to improve health. Digital health expands the concept of eHealth (the cost-effective and secure use of information and communications technologies in support of health and health-related fields) to include digital consumers, with a wider range of smart-devices and connected equipment. It also encompasses other uses of digital technologies for health such as the Internet of things, artificial intelligence, big data and robotics" (WHO, 2021, pp. 39-40).

new digital health technologies with their risks are subject to intense research and debate (Vayena et al., 2018).

3. The use of digital health technologies in clinical practice: ethical issues

Digital health technologies refer to the application of information and communication technology (ICT) to patient health issues and include mobile phones and applications, telemedicine, wearable devices, microprocessors and health information technology, Artificial Intelligence (AI) and Machine Learning (ML), drones. According to literature findings, SSA accounts for the highest burden of disease in the world and the greatest scarcity of healthcare workers (Owhor G. et al, 2023). Despite these challenges, digital health technologies improve healthcare in the region by increasing access to care and enhancing the efficiency of the healthcare system. If, on one hand, SSA is experiencing an expansion of digital health services, on the other, the traditional healthcare systems are usually underdeveloped, understaffed, or not accessible at all. In addition, the application of digital health technologies is heterogeneous across SSA: these include but are not limited to the use of mobile devices in South Africa to benefit from maternal healthcare², in Ghana for detection of fake drugs³, and in Kenya to access digital health-financing platforms. Evidence from the literature shows several telemedicine collaborations and uses of social media tools for health promotion throughout the region. Emerging technologies such as the Internet of Things⁴-related system development, wearables, and sensors have opened possibilities for new, small, and compact diagnostic tools and for easier tracking and monitoring of individuals' health in a hospital setting, or underserved and remote areas. Big data and artificial intelligence have been used for both outbreak control and preparedness, and could be applied to a broad spectrum of diseases in SSA (Holst C. et al., 2020). Among other interesting applications of digital technologies, drones are increasingly being used in Malawi for delivery of blood and medical supplies from one clinic to another and this activity has led to a new academy in Malawi, educating students in the understanding of drones and data (Holst C. et al., 2020; Owhor G. et al, 2023) . Community health

² The South African National Department of Health launched in 2014 the MomConnect platform and roughly 5 million mothers using public antenatal services have registered on it: this platform supports maternal and child health through mobile technology. In particular, pregnant women and new mothers can seek healthcare guidance via an automated chatbot or a human-operated text-based helpdesk (see <https://www.health.gov.za/momconnect/>).

³ The WHO emphasized an existing significant risk of substandard and falsified medical products in low-and middle – income countries: 1) “substandard medical products deny patients access to safe, effective, high-quality products. While their substandard quality may not have been intentional, they can have inadequate therapeutic effectiveness and, in some cases, pose serious risks to patient safety, particularly in vulnerable patient populations”; 2) “falsified medical products have been deliberately designed, manufactured and/or supplied in such a way as to fraudulently misrepresent their identity, composition or source”. The detection of these products is challenging and is key to safeguarding patient safety and public health (see WHO, *Global Surveillance and Monitoring System for substandard and falsified medical products: activity report, August 2017-December 2021*, Geneva, 2024).

A phone-based system called mPedigree was launched in Ghana, in 2007, to face the issue of fake drugs: it is an innovative anti-counterfeit ICT software application that aims at empowering patients in areas with low literacy and low technical capacity via a free text message service to verify their medication's safety; users can check the origin and authenticity of drug treatments before use (see https://mpedigree.com/eng/?page_id=155; last accessed: 3 January 2025).

⁴ Internet of things refers to “a system of interrelated computing devices, mechanical and digital machines, objects, animals or people that are provided with unique identifiers and the ability to transfer data over a network without requiring human-to-human or human-to computer interaction” (WHO, 2021).

workers throughout the region have the opportunity to register vital events with various apps that feed into national vital registration systems: for instance, District Health Information Software 2 is changing the digital ecosystems for monitoring and analysing disease patterns, populations, and outbreaks, by gathering data collected routinely in healthcare facilities and communities (Holst C. et al., 2020).

Moreover, a Digitized Care Management System was implemented by the World Food Program (WFP) and Famoco in South Sudan, Uganda, Tajikistan and Madagascar to provide healthcare assistance and monitoring within WFP nutrition programs, whereas, in Nigeria, a mobile application (Lifebank) connects hospitals, doctors, blood banks, dispatch riders, to facilitate delivery of medical samples, oxygen and rare medicines.

Digital technology also contributed decisively to mitigation actions aimed at reducing the effects of COVID-19 pandemic on vulnerable health systems in SSA through several ways including contact tracing, lockdown enforcement, public awareness and virtual learning (Owhor G. et al, 2023).

Among the main challenges concerning the use of digital health technologies, SSA is confronted with the problem of poor internet penetration compared to developed countries. Ensuring access to quality internet services is relevant for a thriving digital health scenario. Technologies such as telemedicine and the use of electronic records would be inefficient without adequate internet coverage reaching the population. Challenges related to poor internet coverage are exacerbated by poor electricity supply. Evidence from the literature shows that electricity shortage is a major barrier to the use of digital health technology in this geographical area. Power outage occurs frequently in Nigeria, South Sudan, Chad, Malawi, Niger and Sierra Leone, among others. In addition, the healthcare system of SSA is hampered by inadequate financing and leadership: this is a huge hurdle, given the high costs for the implementation of digital technology (i.e., the costs associated with the supply of hardware, software, training facilities and maintenance). A major source of funding in the region concerns donor funding, therefore, these countries may be unable to afford the high costs of digital health. The latter's development in SSA equally relies on the knowledge of the health workforce about digital technologies, which is often inadequate, according to literature findings. Ensuring an appropriate training for the workforce will be necessary to reap the opportunities offered by digital health (Owhor G. et al, 2023).

Alongside promising solutions, many people in SSA currently face several real-life barriers in accessing digital health technologies, which are likely to result in health inequities: most of these barriers are associated with the urban–rural and gender divide, lack of available digital devices due to affordability issues and digital illiteracy or low digital literacy, as well as shortage of connectivity and electricity. As digital health implementations rely on the specific context, populations need tailored digital content in their own language, not only for access to healthcare systems but also for disease prevention. As regularly mentioned in the literature, health information and digital health solutions and interventions should be co-designed with local communities, in order to ensure acceptability and understanding, which can also be jeopardized by health literacy issues. In this regard, a project conducted by The Non-Discriminating Access for Digital Inclusion consortium, in SSA, focused on co-designing together with the communities, digital health messages for disease management and prevention for HIV/AIDS, tuberculosis, and zoonotic diseases, based on multistakeholder insights. This initiative also considered the local context in terms of connectivity and access to mobile devices (Holst C. et al., 2020).

Literature findings consider ethical issues in digital health at a multidimensional level: first, they are related to fair access and how digital health technologies are used. Second, different stakeholders from the medical and non-medical, public and private arena are involved (i.e. users, a wide array of providers of digital health technologies – public or governmental, private companies, namely app technology start-ups, pharmaceutical or medical device companies - other stakeholders are physicians responsible for medical programmes, researchers for data analytics or government and non-governmental organizations, insurers and society that are generally committed to implementing digital health initiatives) raising new challenges regarding governance structures, emphasizing the need for identifying clear responsibilities.: for instance, digital health technology designers, developers and providers are entrusted with the responsibility to ensure an ethical use and implementation of these technologies. Honouring this responsibility also fosters their trustworthiness, which can be improved through the elaboration of procedural values guiding governance for providers (pointing out key elements for fair digital health provision). Third, ethical issues are, on the one hand, linked to technical aspects, namely how to protect data (e.g. secure storage, firewalls, etc.); on the other hand, they focus on challenges related to general governance (i.e., accountability and transparency). Alongside these issues, which can even result in physical, psychological or social harms to individuals, there are also digital health opportunities to establish fairer health systems (Brall C. et al., 2019).

Digital health technologies use large amounts of human health data: generally, the collection of health data is mediated by officially licensed medical devices, such as diagnostic instruments managed by health professionals in clinical settings and following rigorous regulatory requirements. In addition, clinical data are typically stored in public health registries, at hospitals or in the archives of individual physicians. Digital health technologies, instead, involve “connecting health-related data, including data generated by patients themselves, and harnessing the medical potential of technological tools of common usage, such as smartphones, apps, social media. Most of these tools are not initially conceived for medical use and are not marketed as medical devices” (Vayena et al., 2018, p. 1).

Digital health technologies are mainly characterized by the fact that through wearable, portable, ingestible or otherwise implantable devices – they generate a “seamless flow of critical medical data between patients, their families and their physicians” (Vayena et al., 2018, p 1). Hence, digital tools are aimed at generating a *circulation of data* from patients (patient-generated data), to devices and/or health professionals (who deal with data analysis), and then back to devices that eventually provide the patient with information regarding their health status and how to manage it. In this context, phenotypic and behavioural information, as well as data about socioeconomic status and dwelling environment, need to be collected.

Digital health is an “evolving health data ecosystem”, as E. Vayena defines it, a space that equally encompasses data gathered by healthcare services, namely electronic health records, genetic or genomic data, diagnostic data. Literature findings mention that due to their volume, velocity variety veracity (the so-called “4 V’s”) and propensity to be analysed through data-mining techniques, these data qualify as big data. This expanded set of health-relevant data is expected to bring about significant advancements in medicine (for instance, supporting people in monitoring their health condition or patients in coping with a particular health issue, inferring health-related problems earlier on, providing personalised treatments, reducing costs and inefficiencies, and fostering medical discovery and expediting drug development), as well as improvements in the organization of healthcare systems.

However, to leverage on digital health technologies, ethical challenges need to be tackled: Mining large-scale data repositories raises issues related to oversight mechanism, transparency, data management, privacy protection, fairness. Other issues are linked to the composition of the repositories and to the tools used to mine the data they include. For instance, the representativeness of the datasets (avoiding biases in sample compositions) used for product development and the reliability of analytic tools to mine such datasets can affect the development of effective digital health services and devices.

More specifically, literature findings report a set of ethical values, which may be jeopardized in the context of digital health technologies (Brall C. et al., 2019; Coles D. et al., 2018; Laflamme L. et al., 2020; Mbunge E. et al., 2021; Shaw J. et al., 2021, 2024; Vayena et al., 2018; Zarif A., 2022):

- a) *Human dignity*: digital health tools should only be applied when the dignity of the patient can be protected. For example, in the case of using telemedicine⁵ in hospital settings, the ways of informing the patient of a potentially bad news should take into account the centrality of the dignity of the patient. On this ground, distant technologies (using screens) should be avoided when disclosing news which put the patient in a vulnerable situation. In this context, preferable options should rely on personal and face-to-face communication, in order to protect the dignity of patients in vulnerable situations. Here autonomy should be understood as recognizing the patients' choice with respect to communication channels and adapting the delivery of healthcare to patients' needs. By the same token, patients who do not wish to be hospitalized can stay at home longer and be better supported in their home environment through telemedicine. Their dignity and quality of life can therefore be preserved through the use of these technologies.
- b) *Privacy and security*: the increasing availability of data sources, coupled with advanced analytics applications for many different purposes, pose challenges in relation to privacy protection. Standard mechanisms of protection (i.e. anonymisation, and pseudonymisation) underwent excessive expansion in this area of new capabilities: in particular, full anonymisation refers to the complete and irreversible removal of any information from a dataset that could result in data subject re-identification (in this case, there is no relationship between data and data subjects, therefore, re-identification is impossible), whereas pseudonymisation involves processing personal data in ways that the data cannot be assigned to a data subject without the use of additional information (i.e. the data subject is protected by a code safely stored by researchers through technical measures of protection, but this mechanism cannot rule out the chances of possible re-identification): if, on the one hand, full anonymisation is clearly safer, on the other hand, it proves to be less interesting for scientists, as they also need clinical and personal data to achieve their research goals. Hence, pseudonymisation is the mechanism of protection generally used since it ensures a significant level of protection, even if not full protection. Moreover, informed consent for data use can be *specific*, when the data use is known at the time of data collection; or *broad*, when it includes the range of future uses in research for which consent is given (CIOMS, 2016). However, informed consent can barely encompass the comprehensive list of all

⁵ Telemedicine refers to “the delivery of health care services, where distance is a critical factor, by all health-care professionals using information and communications technologies for the exchange of valid information for diagnosis, treatment and prevention of disease and injuries, research and evaluation, and the continuing education of health care workers, with the aim of advancing the health of individuals and communities” (WHO, 2021, p. 43)

potential future data uses. Data security has also been an issue, with cyber attacks, hacking of databases and data kidnapping being reported frequently. These challenges can be tackled with reliance on adequate technologies, monitoring and evaluation of security systems, transparency and accountability mechanisms, such as legal remedies and compensation for privacy harms stemming from security breaches.

- c) *Trust*: trustworthy digital health activities need more than privacy protection. Features of trust encompass meaningful human oversight, safety, transparency, accountability, explainability, autonomy, responsibility, benefit sharing and more clarity regarding data ownership and data control, fairness and justice. Hence, trustworthiness cannot only be attained through innovative consent models providing for more or less control of data uses, but consent innovation has to equally ensure clarity and understandability (tailored to the condition of the patient) on how individuals and communities will benefit from digital health developments, by oversight mechanisms that protect common interests and by accountability mechanisms that can support public scrutiny (Vayena et al., 2018).
- d) *Accountability*: digital health opens up new opportunities in the field of automated data mining for clinical or public health decisions, where accountability is crucial. Therefore, the use of these innovative technologies involves significant adaptations in current accountability standards. For example, when it comes to digital epidemiology, data mining can be used to analyse free, unstructured text from social networks, in order to forecast the risk of spread of infectious diseases. In addition, mobile technologies can be used to target specific populations with health-related information, which can provide support in curbing the spread of infectious diseases. These innovative solutions can increase the speed and accuracy of health dynamics monitoring, resulting in more targeted and effective interventions. Nevertheless, an early adoption of these technologies could bring about an inefficient use of public resources, unnecessary public alarm and individual harm from dispensable medications. Clinical practice will increasingly rely on AI⁶ algorithms for diagnosis, treatment decisions and surgical procedures. (i.e. AI-assisted surgical tools that use machine learning algorithms to analyze patient data and optimize surgical strategies or AI-driven imaging technologies, that provide real-time, high-resolution images during surgery, supporting accurate decision-making). If, on the one hand, advancements in this field have the potential to considerably improve the quality of healthcare services for patients (the spectrum of these technologies span from merely providing assistance to practitioners, to possibly one day being fully autonomous from human supervision), as growing sophistication could result in greater accuracy; on the other, to the extent that AI-guided tools become autonomous, human operators will be reluctant to disregard their decisions. Therefore, AI-guided medical devices have the potential to put existing norms of professional accountability at risk, in clinical practice, adding complexity to tracking responsibility of health practitioners. Hence, the elaboration of *ad hoc* standards, strongly supported by evidence, is required to guide the adoption of digital health technologies in clinical practice (Vayena et al., 2018).

⁶ Artificial Intelligence (AI) refers to “an area of computer science that emphasizes the simulation of human intelligence processes by machines” (WHO, 2021, p. 39).

- e) *Equitable access*: ethical issues surrounding the use of digital health technologies arise even before users access these tools. At this early stage, ethical considerations particularly hinge on logistic and resource-related aspects, linked to an equitable access to digital health services based on affordability of and access to technological equipment. In this context, the availability of these services is equally crucial: for underserved communities and populations (such as people suffering from rare diseases, elderly or homeless) digital health technologies might not be offered or even developed. Fairness and equity in access are key elements, which need to be safeguarded and considered already when designing and developing these digital health tools. Integrating such ethical approaches in the designing phase is referred to as ‘ethics by design’ (Brall C. et al., 2019). The developers of digital health technologies have a moral responsibility to design digital tools aligned with ethical forethoughts and aspects (for example, when designing algorithms for artificial intelligence, that represent all parts of the population and leave no ground for bias and ensuing discrimination). However, the use of digital health technologies can lead to inequalities in access that are not limited to technology affordability, but focus on the individual’s technological ability and capacity to handle e-health devices. If specific populations are excluded from using these technologies, for example for age-related socialization and digital illiteracy, as pointed out by C. Brall, there is a significant risk of “unjust health system 4.0” (Brall C. et al., 2019, p. 19). Nevertheless, digital health technologies can equally facilitate the inclusion of population groups which experience barriers to access conventional healthcare services (as is often the case in SSA). These barriers encompass geographical distance to reach medical settings in general or specific healthcare professionals, or the physical inability to regularly travel to the medical sites. In this context, digital tools can improve fairness in health provision access by ensuring healthcare coverage in areas and for people with previously limited access to health services. At the same time, a potential extension in health coverage can have a positive impact on global health and be assessed as an effective action to foster equality of opportunity.
- f) *Autonomy and informed consent*: for patients to be able to assess whether to use digital tools and express a voluntary decision in this context, truthful information about the benefits and risks of digital health methods has to be provided to them. For this reason, open communication, technical training and education should be available. Patients’ choice must be voluntary and freedom not jeopardized by any sort of incentive (either of financial nature or in terms of prioritization of patients that rely on digital tools, when they seek medical care in nondigital, conventional healthcare settings). Moreover, the voluntary decision not to use digital health technologies must not be sanctioned or lead to a lack of access to health services. In addition, users should receive appropriate information about how their data being collected for health-related purposes. Despite the fact that digital epidemiology techniques using aggregate information (for instance from social media posts about flu symptoms) for health purposes could give some indication about the diffusion of diseases, it also entails the risk of establishing a surveillance society through digital health. This use should be forbidden by law and tangibly avoided.

Alongside traditional informed consent models, that are meant to inform patients and place significant emphasis on avoiding harm to the individual during the procedure, for a limited time, consideration

should be given to new models of informed consent tailored to digital health specificities. The latter should not merely envisage intended and unintended uses of data shared by informed users, but should even focus on a larger time span, when data storage (and potential use) occurs for an extensive period of time. Moreover, specific digital health tools, for instance in cases where genetic data are collected, acquire knowledge not only about individuals, but also about their genetically related family members. Literature findings mention the need to review current models of informed consent to face the challenges posed by digital health and tailor the consent process accordingly to safeguard autonomy for everyone and encourage fair data uses (Brall C. et al., 2019).

- g) *Fairness in data storage, sharing and ownership*: ethical issues regarding the use of digital health technologies emerge in relation to data storage, sharing and ownership. Along with key ethical aspects related to security, privacy, confidentiality, discrimination, unintended uses of data and right to know or not to know results about incidental findings (namely, findings having potential health importance for research participants, discovered unintentionally during research, but going beyond the aims of the research project) these elements equally affect a fair use of digital health. First, data have to be stored safely, preventing forms of unauthorized access through hacking or other fraud that may lead to discrimination and stigmatization, if confidential information is disclosed inappropriately. In addition, a fair use of data should be ensured in relation to the ownership of data (i.e. who owns the data and who is custodian of data: data collectors, users themselves, governments, public organizations, etc.). As mentioned in the literature, digital health technologies offer individuals increased access to their medical information, which increases their freedom to become more autonomous with regard to their health. Although, what can be deemed beneficial for some, equally can turn out to be detrimental for others, who are unable to manage their own health and are at risk of being overburdened. This aspect requires careful consideration (Brall C. et al., 2019).

4. The use of digital health technologies in clinical trials⁷: ethical issues

Digital health technologies can be used to modernise clinical trials by improving efficiency, accuracy, and patient engagement: in the context of SSA, the literature mentions reliance on decentralised trials, which use digital technologies to conduct siteless, virtual, remote and home-based trials (WHO, 2021), with the advantage of reducing the need for physical site visits, increasing patient diversity, and improving trial accessibility (Nebie E. et al., 2023), as well as mobile health (mhealth) platforms for clinical trial data collection via mobile devices, aimed at enabling patient recruitment, facilitating real-time data collection, and improving patient adherence (Dam J. van et al., 2017; Harris P. A, 2021).

As for the former, SSA has experienced the adoption of decentralised clinical trials (DCTs) as a mitigation and efficiency improvement strategy during the COVID-19 pandemic (Nebie E. et al., 2023). The

⁷ Clinical trial refers to “a type of research that studies new tests and treatments and evaluates their effects on human health outcomes. People volunteer to take part in clinical trials to test medical interventions including drugs, cells and other biological products, surgical procedures, radiological procedures, devices, behavioural treatments and preventive care” (see https://www.who.int/health-topics/clinical-trials#tab=tab_1; last accessed: 3 January 2025).

implementation of DCTs focuses on the use of digital health technologies and encompasses all remote engagement with trial participants. The concept of DCTs is participant-centred. Before the COVID-19 pandemic, electronic data capture (EDC)⁸, electronic health records⁹ and telemedicine were the key digital tools in clinical trials. Recently, the use of wearable devices for electronic patient-reported outcome (ePRO)¹⁰ and electronic clinical outcome assessment, as well as artificial intelligence, have been coming to the fore. Nevertheless, in sub-Saharan Africa, the transition to DCTs is at an early stage (Nebie E. et al., 2023).. With the COVID-19 pandemic, DCTs were quickly started in some research institutions in sub-Saharan Africa (for instance, in Burkina Faso, Kenya, Mali, South Africa) to pursue ongoing clinical trials. User-friendly and multifunctional digital solutions (with possibility to measure several parameters, for example, pulse, temperature and respiratory rate with one device) were developed in SSA.

In this context, according to literature findings, there has not been reliance on wearable sensor devices for remote monitoring of clinical trials participants (Nebie E. et al., 2023). DCTs could decrease the burden of trials on participants in terms of travel and time, especially for participants living in remote areas. This could improve the geographical diversity in participants' recruitment. During the COVID-19 pandemic, DCTs promoted hybrid or centralised monitoring as well as remote and real-time access to the data allowing for timely corrective measures. Moreover, digitalised documentation, electronic case report forms and trial files facilitated the continuity of clinical trials.

However, the trend towards the digitalisation of all the processes of clinical trials with the use of various electronic platforms and systems could also become burdensome and a threat to trial quality. Hence, integrated and/or interoperable systems will be needed to avoid additional workload and errors due to loss of data or operational inaccuracies (Nebie E. et al., 2023).

Alongside the opportunities, it is possible to identify a set of ethical challenges regarding the digitalisation of trials in SSA, stemming from the literature:

- 1) *Usability and practicability of the technology*: namely, the ability of researchers and participants to manage new technologies can be inadequate, posing the issue of digital literacy, as well as the lack of stable internet connectivity in some rural settings of SSA, initial set-up costs, digital tools' maintenance complexity and acceptability, especially when it comes to wearable devices;
- 2) *shift from conventional clinical trials to decentralised clinical trials*: this could jeopardise the quality of clinical trials and put data validity at risk. Therefore, a careful and timely planning for an appropriate digital education is necessary;

⁸ Electronic Data Capture (EDC) systems collect and manage clinical trial data electronically. Their application focuses on streamlining data collection, reducing errors, and facilitating real-time data access and analysis.

⁹ The integration of electronic health records allows clinical trial data to be linked with routine clinical data, facilitating patient recruitment, accessing real-world data.

¹⁰ Electronic Patient-Reported Outcome (ePRO) systems collect data directly from patients about their health condition and treatment via electronic means. This technology aims at capturing real-time patient feedback, improving patient engagement.

- 3) *shift from a site-centric to a patient-centric approach*: patient-centric technologies should be tailored to the context. In DCTs, participants have important responsibilities for data collection, outcome reporting and/or clinical outcome assessment. These activities were previously conducted onsite by the research teams and sometimes with the support of community health workers. This might become a challenge, particularly in settings with low literacy rates. This issue could be mitigated with adequate information and instructions about the tools intended for participants use;
- 4) *ethical review*: to fit decentralised clinical trials within SSA clinical trial regulations and their acceptance by ethics committees and regulatory authorities were identified as challenges in the literature; mitigation strategies were suggested, such as adequate communication, education of participants and researchers, members of National Ethics Committees (NECs) and regulatory authority bodies regarding the risk–benefit assessment of DCTs;
- 5) *socio-cultural aspects*: beyond clinical trials’ social acceptability issues, digital tools could create misunderstanding, trust disruption and reduce population participation in future clinical trials. Adequate and timely communication was suggested to address this issue. In addition, to address acceptance issues, patient groups should be involved in the selection of patient-centred technologies;
- 6) *researcher-participant relationship*: there is a risk of dehumanizing trials and of disruption of the face-to-face relationship between researchers and participants;
- 7) *research team responsibility*: it is important to ensure that the shift of responsibility to the patients will not waive or delay the trial oversight by the research team. In this perspective, transparent communication plays a central role, along with an effective interaction between researchers and participants, and the participants’ability to attend and meet the research team anytime during trial participation.

Clinical trials in sub-Saharan Africa are focused on infectious diseases, especially acute illnesses except for tuberculosis and HIV. As the research institutions in this geographical area are striving to tackle the epidemiological transition with the rising burden of chronic and non-communicable diseases, DCTs have the potential to gain increasing interest. (Nebie E. et al., 2023).

As for the use of mobile health (mhealth) platforms for clinical trial data collection, the literature mentions an interesting pilot study conducted in Kenya: the mobile platform used in this study is an open source cloud-based platform for health programmes that supports the development of data capture tools using mobile devices. This pilot study showed the feasibility and utility of an innovative mobile digital platform for data collection and management in low-resource settings. User satisfaction was high, mainly due to improved operational efficiencies and data quality processes (Dam J. van et al., 2017).

Another study focused on the development of a Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap) Mobile Application to allow research teams the option of using a non-internet-connected mobile device for field data collection, with synchronization to a “parent” REDCap database project whenever internet

connectivity could be established. This application could be useful in those geographical areas experiencing connectivity problems. Several SSA countries were involved in this study (South Africa, Kenya, Rwanda, Nigeria, Ethiopia, Malawi, Ghana, and Sudan): the literature reports that designing and deploying a general use mobile application platform to support diverse clinical and translational research studies across a large number of geographic regions is more challenging than establishing a targeted platform for use by a single team supporting a single project. Choosing a mobile application development framework is important and should also rely on targeted end-user technology expectations (Harris P. A, 2021).

It is possible to identify a range of ethical issues raised by the use of mobile phones for clinical trials:

- a) *informed consent, risk communication and cultural issues*: researchers have the duty to inform the participants and obtain informed consent from participants, prior to the use of mHealth technologies in research. In this context, participants must be informed about, and understand the possible benefits and risks of these technologies, and then decide freely and voluntarily whether to participate or not in a research study. Nevertheless, mHealth risks are complex, and need to be communicated effectively (Coles D. et al., 2018). In particular, researchers in SSA are confronted with a broad spectrum of challenges when dealing with informed consent in this specific area, as in data-intensive research in general. These challenges encompass data illiteracy (Moyo E. et al., 2023), use of technical terms and language multiplicity (Omutoko L. et al., 2024). Literature findings highlight that the linguistic diversity in SSA is a major barrier to informed consent: researchers are often required to translate complex technical terms and data-related concepts into local languages to facilitate information and comprehension. This can result in a complicated or even unfeasible activity, due to the number of languages used or spoken in different countries. For instance, by 2022 there were over 2000 languages in Africa, with Nigeria accounting for 520 languages, followed by Cameroon (277 languages), Democratic Republic of Congo (214 languages), Ghana (83 languages), Kenya (68 languages), South Africa (31 languages) and Zimbabwe (23 languages; Omutoko L. et al., 2024). Ensuring translations that accurately grasp the intended meaning of data-related concepts is problematic, also because African language lexicons often do not have up-to-date translations for scientific terms. This challenge is exacerbated by the fact that many researchers lack vernacular linguistic competency, since they completed their science education in a foreign language. Potential research participants may also have low levels of data literacy, inadequate awareness of potential risks and benefits, or they may belong to communities with limited experience in research participation. SSA is dominated by a variety of languages and cultures resulting in cultural and contextual differences (Iyioke, I. et al., 2024) including paternalism in healthcare that can hinder engaged and empowered participation in conversations on data-related issues. Moreover, limited availability of resources may hamper the development of communication materials or investment in educational initiatives for research participants and capacity-building of researchers, which are essential to be able to convey and understand data-related concepts. These aspects emphasize the need for researchers to communicate effectively with research participants. As stated by the Declaration of Helsinki, researchers can only obtain voluntary informed consent “after ensuring that the potential subject has understood the information” (World Medical Association, 2024). A successful participation in research is based on using easily comprehensible language. Terminology such as big data, data sources, data subjects, data

privacy and data protection are used across different academic fields of research. Although, interpretations of these terms are often not transparent or universally accepted. This may further complicate the informed consent process, which is also contextual and may be influenced by multilingualism, culture and economic status (CIOMS, 2016). It is therefore important for researchers, RECs, and the research communities to develop mechanisms aimed at fostering participants' understanding: the information should be conveyed in ways that minimise possible misunderstandings or misinterpretations and facilitate content clarity with regard to the consent form. There are suggestions in the literature to also include visuals or pictographs, given that a depiction used in any language often has the ability to convey the same message. Nevertheless, even if using appropriate language or visuals, differences in cultural meaning or interpretation could still remain. This points out how community engagement plays a central role to ensure appropriate use of visuals or images in diverse research contexts (Omutoko L. et al., 2024; Tham J. et al., 2022; Palazzani et al., 2019).

- b) *minimizing data collection*: mHealth collects a large amount of data about participants' lifestyles and activities, over a long time span. A potential risk in this context concerns collecting excessive amounts of raw data to maximize the information extracted by the research team;
- c) *data security*: a global research environment increasingly requires the sharing of data in publicly available repositories. The case of an alleged breach of smartphone users' privacy by manufacturers of popular smartphone apps for Apple and Android devices highlights this risk. The manufacturers are alleged to have gathered information from personal address books on the phones of Kenyan users, stored it on their own computers, and transmitted it without the knowledge of its owners, all of which demonstrates how difficult it is to guarantee privacy when using smartphones. Potential violations of privacy include hacking of personal data with the known likelihood of identity theft and financial losses, computer malware and virus programs, and malevolent apps planted by developers who steal data for commercial or criminal purposes (Coles D. et al., 2018);
- d) *privacy and proportionate tracking*: continuous or intermittent recording and transmission of detailed information about where people are and their regular habits may breach privacy and confidentiality. There are risks of unintended insight into a participant's behaviour disclosing information beyond the profiles that are scientifically justified and for which data collection was used. Informed consent also becomes challenging in this context, as privacy may be violated in ways unforeseen by both researchers and/or participants. Text messages (SMS) can be read by persons other than the intended recipient; messages can be forwarded and can remain on unsecured devices indefinitely, resulting in a possible unintended disclosure of a medical condition (Coles D. et al., 2018);
- e) *avoiding exploitation*: research conducted with mHealth apps often requires the participant to have a smartphone. If researchers specifically target those who do not already own new devices or other modes of mobile technology, the prospect of being given access to such technology may unduly influence them to take part. Potential participants should not, however, be excluded from mHealth monitoring benefits if they cannot afford a device capable of

supporting the app or connect with networks capable of transmitting potentially large volumes of data. However, this requirement needs careful assessment (Coles D. et al., 2018).

From a general perspective, in relation to digital health technologies in clinical research, the Council for International Organizations of Medical Sciences (CIOMS) emphasizes that “in low-resource settings, researchers and innovators face tremendous challenges, including the lack of technical training, basic infrastructure, research tools, financial resources, and up-to-date access to scientific information through the internet. Of note, the unchecked availability of scientific data, as recently observed during the COVID-19 pandemic, can also lead to an increasing risk of misinformation of scientists and the public alike. All these obstacles impede developing and implementing innovative and low-cost technologies. The availability of communication technology—ranging from basic cellphone coverage to 5G—and internet bandwidth has a major impact on the level of penetration of digital technologies. Low internet upload/download speeds have been major impediments to date” (CIOMS, 2021).

5. Ethical review challenges

Alongside using digital health technologies as valuable tools to innovate and streamline clinical trials procedures, they can also be tested to improve patient treatment management for clinical practice¹¹.

Nevertheless, as clearly stated in the D2.1 report¹², a number of challenges can be devised when it comes to identifying ethical review processes for digital health technologies: an appropriate ethical assessment of these technologies depends on a clear understanding of what constitutes digital health technologies, as well as of the ethical and regulatory landscape in sub-Saharan Africa when reviewing clinical research protocols, including clinical trials. D2.1 findings largely reveal a widespread gap in knowledge regarding digital health technologies across the region: many stakeholders—especially National Ethics Committees (NECs) and National Regulatory Authorities (NRAs)—demonstrate limited

¹¹ In this context, the literature reports several studies conducted in SSA, among others: a trial to reduce unnecessary caesarean deliveries in Burkina Faso, promoting the use of clinical algorithms for caesarean decision-making using in-site training, audits and feedback of caesarean indications and SMS reminders (Kaboré et al., 2019); trials involving text messages to increase attendance to follow-up cervical cancer screening appointments among HPV-positive Tanzanian women and AI-supported diabetic retinopathy screening in Tanzania (Linde D. S. et al., 2017; Cleland C. R. et al., 2024); a trial of a mobile video entertainment-education intervention to promote exclusive breastfeeding in South Africa (Adam M. et al., 2019); trials involving a mobile phone-based interactive voice response software on tuberculosis treatment outcomes and a mobile application in improving adverse drug reaction reporting by healthcare professionals in Uganda, in the context of resource-limited settings with high illiteracy rates (Byonanebye D. et al., 2021; Kiguba R. et al., 2022); trials involving mobile phone based remote monitoring system for palliative care, mobile-health on maternal health care service utilization and mobile phone text message reminders on improving completeness and timeliness of routine childhood vaccinations in Ethiopia (Carey N. et al., 2023; Gelano T. F. et al., 2018; Mekonnen Z. A., 2019); trials involving mHealth-based integrated management of diabetes in primary healthcare and mobile health technology and community health workers to identify and refer caesarean-related surgical site infections in rural Rwanda (Lygidakis C. et al., 2019; Sonderman K. A. et al., 2018); a trial involving maternal deaths surveillance and response system at the health district level in Guinea through digital communication tools (Millimouno T. M. et al., 2017); trials on SMS messaging strategy to reduce neonatal mortality and to support maternally administered childhood mid-upper arm circumference monitoring and expand malnutrition screening in Kenya (Ronen K. et al., 2021; Tickell K. D., 2020); a trial involving mobile phone text messaging in promotion of breastfeeding among women living with HIV in South Africa (Zunza M. et al., 2017; 2023).

¹² For a thorough reconstruction of the legal infrastructure for digital health technologies in SSA, see D2.1 report.

awareness of the ethical, regulatory, and legal implications associated with digital health technologies. Nevertheless, the evidence indicates that when expertise was lacking, NECs and NRAs sought external support by engaging and consulting experts in the relevant fields.

Moreover, findings show there is no regulation of processes or guidelines for reviewing protocols for digital health technologies: while general guidelines and policies exist and provide a basic ethical framework for protocol development, they do not specifically address digital health technologies. In relation to the design and implementation of these technologies, no dedicated guidelines are in place.

In addition, most NEC members have little or no experience in assessing clinical research protocols, including clinical trials, that involve digital health technologies. There is a clear need to strengthen capacity for reviewing research protocols with digital health components, ensuring that digital health concepts are well understood and that ethical and regulatory concerns can be properly recognized. Enhanced capacity is equally required for NRA members to develop guidelines that can effectively support and govern the review of digital health technologies.

The ethical review procedures applied to studies involving digital health technologies are largely the same as those used for non-digital health technology research, with no tailored considerations for protocols incorporating these technologies. As many NEC members lack comprehensive understanding of the ethical implications of digital health technologies, reviewers are consequently unable to fully evaluate the risks associated with their deployment

One of the pivotal steps taken during the ethical review of digital health technologies is to ensure the safety of the technologies: the risks related to the use of these technologies are assessed to guarantee the protection of research participants. However, due to a lack of full understanding of how these technologies function, the members of NECs capacity to perform an effective risk-benefit assessment proves inadequate. In this regard, major concerns are reported about the likelihood of misuse of the technology, privacy and confidentiality issues with data use, lack of transparency in data sharing, as well as unclear levels of responsibility when using the technology. In terms of data security, there are also concerns regarding the possibility of undermining data confidentiality by relying on others for assistance in using digital health technologies. Other questions raised by NEC members focus on data storage practices associated with these technologies and data ownership, particularly in cases where study data are stored outside the country in which the research is conducted and, at times, beyond the control of the local researchers who generated the data. According to D2.1 findings, this situation is viewed as problematic, in terms of risk of exploitation of study participants, which could ultimately affect trust in the research with digital health technologies.

A number of difficulties were identified in the review of protocols: key challenges are related to a limited ability to evaluate community acceptance of the technology involved in a specific study, participant vulnerability (i.e. even the design of a study may introduce new forms of vulnerability for certain research participants, especially if the technologies pose environmental or contextual challenges, particularly their effects on local communities, such as the circumstances of people living in rural areas. There is therefore a need to understand how the introduction of such technologies can create vulnerabilities for individuals who might not have been considered vulnerable in their absence) and the exclusion of potential participants due to language barriers or low levels of digital literacy. Concerns about fair access to the technology were also highlighted, particularly in relation to

telemedicine. For example, the use of smartphone-based telemedicine for women can raise ethical issues, as not all women who might have been eligible to participate in studies relying on these tools have access to smartphones across the region.

Another key consideration is evaluating whether and to what degree a technology might widen or reduce existing health inequities. Some digital health solutions may advantage certain groups while disadvantaging others. Therefore, it is important to assess the potential impact of a technology on equitable access to health services and determine whether its use is likely to exacerbate or mitigate disparities.

As recalled earlier, members of ethics committees require specialized knowledge and skills to effectively review and identify ethical concerns related to the use of digital health technologies. Targeted training is necessary to ensure a thorough understanding of digital health concepts. In addition, there is a need to establish structured training mechanisms that account for emerging technologies and promote collaboration with relevant institutional stakeholders. Coordinated efforts across sub-Saharan African countries are necessary to establish a distinct approval process specifically for protocols that incorporate digital health technologies and relevant criteria guiding NEC members should be set out for the ethical review process of these technologies.

6. For an ethical design of digital health technologies in sub-saharan africa: recommendations

As highlighted earlier in this report, traditional healthcare systems in SSA are usually underdeveloped, understaffed, and inaccessible to underserved populations. Despite these challenges, there is the assumption that digital health technologies could drastically improve healthcare provision in the region. Even with such optimism, questions of balancing the anticipated benefits of new digital health technologies with their associated risks are subject to intense debate across research, policy and practice landscape (Vayena et al., 2018). Therefore, through focus group discussions conducted in the STRATEGIC project, we identified and mapped core African values and principles that can be embedded into the design and deployment of digital health technologies.

In this context, values are considered as fundamental beliefs that guide or motivate attitudes or actions (Friedman and Kahn, 2007); whereas principles are the rules/standards that help us act in line with values (Mittelstadt, 2019).

In terms of shared values, it is common knowledge that relational ethical values are embedded in many African social and organizational systems. Ubuntu philosophy posits that “a person is a person through other persons” as foundational to an African responsible innovation approach. Ubuntu challenges Western notions of the self as autonomous and independent, instead promoting communal responsibility, reciprocity, and intergenerational justice. Values such as relational autonomy, collective accountability, and social harmony are essential ethical anchors that should shape how innovation is conceptualized, developed and practiced in African contexts.

Within the innovation life cycle, focus group participants identified understanding of context, privacy requirements, digital divide and contextual knowledge as the key considerations in designing digital health technologies for clinical research and practice. Participants also emphasize that technological accessibility, literacy level, language requirement and trust level vary widely across contexts; thus, the need for ensuring adaptability and sustainability of designed and deployed innovation heightened. Other factors such as sociocultural beliefs, equality and inclusivity requirements are deemed as key values that should inform the conceptualization and evaluation of digital health technologies for the wider SSA context.

In the terms of core elements to inform the design and adoption of digital health technologies, there was the call for a shift from technocratic and procedural notions of digital innovation towards concepts of epistemic justice, digital sovereignty, and relational accountability. In the ideation stage, participants emphasised the need for adopting ethical principles based on community engagement where diverse norms, traditions and cultures are embedded in the processes of design and evaluation. Building on the principle of participatory design, some have suggested that long-term planning and engagement with communities are necessary for the successful adoption of technologies where ownership of intellectual property and design could ensure that digital health technologies remain viable beyond the duration of projects. This is supported by the fact that when people do not understand how things work, or when things are complicated, they tend to associate these technologies with witchcraft, which in effect might hinder adoption and usage.

In the design stage, participants reported interoperability issues such as data collection, hardware accessibility, localized design as prerequisite for inclusive design. Participants also indicated that digital health technologies should be co-designed with relevant stakeholders such as community of users rather than imported and imposed to local communities. In the development stage, the emphasis was on interoperability, usability, and continual testing considerations in designing digital health technologies.

To ensure adoption, there is the need to validate functionality according to preconceived ideas of what the end project is meant to deliver. Others emphasized the need for design processes to align with already existing institutional and national policies for greater acceptance and replication. In the deployment stage, participants indicated that deployed digital health technologies should be designed in ways that improve existing healthcare systems and not compromise them. Some participants further noted that the adoption of digital health technologies in clinical settings is influenced by the overall maturity and advancement of the healthcare systems and infrastructure in each context. The adoption is also shaped by multiple interrelated factors, ranging from community beliefs, institutional practices, and regulatory reviews. The rollout and scale up of digital health technologies must account for disparities within health systems, as introducing advanced tools in under-resource settings can create unintended inequities.

Infrastructural barriers to deployment such as the lack of reliable electricity and internet access, and stigmatization of imported services require the alignment of new intervention with existing national health data governance strategies that ensures that initiatives are consistent with broader health system priorities and regulatory expectations. Partnerships with governments are often essential for accessing health records and institutional systems, but these collaborations can be complicated by political interests or public image considerations. Participants revealed the situations where

governance over data has encountered inequality due to where servers are situated. Participants expressed frustration with the application of GDPR regulations in multi-country research collaborations, noting that these requirements often conflict with local laws and hinder project implementation. Participants also revealed situations where sovereignty over data has encountered inequality due to where servers are situated and the issues of in-country data storage.

Other points stemming from the discussions included data sovereignty in digital health technologies where there is an agreement on ownership, control, and use of health data, especially when non-governmental entities are involved. While partnerships are necessary for widening access, ensuring sovereignty also means protecting communities' rights and guaranteeing fair benefit-sharing from data-driven outcomes.

Overall, the focus group discussions identified ethical and legal issues raised by digital health technologies for clinical research and practice and ways in which specific values and principles could inform the design and adoption of digital health technologies to signal a shift from technocratic and procedural notions of digital innovation towards concepts of epistemic justice, digital sovereignty, and relational accountability.

The analysis carried out in this report of the ethical issues arising from the use of digital health technologies in SSA is not intended to be exhaustive. Rather, this work highlights the absence of a clear boundary between the ethical questions raised in clinical practice and those related to clinical trials, as many ethical considerations are relevant to both domains. Likewise, the ethical challenges discussed are not unique to SSA: some are common to all low-resource settings, while others can be applied to different geographical contexts. Nevertheless, the literature review conducted in this deliverable indicates that certain issues can reasonably be expected to be particularly relevant in the context of SSA. In particular, among the key ethical challenges devised, several ones are common to clinical practice and clinical trials settings, and a set of preliminary recommendations can be set out, to be further developed in WP4:

- **Context-specific interventions and fair access:** an unequal access to digital health technologies, in SSA, is likely to result in health inequities; there are disparities not only between rich and poor countries in the use of digital health technologies across the region, but also divides between urban and rural areas and between zones of peace and zones of war; gender divide is another issue if one considers that in some areas (especially in rural ones) women do not have access to smartphones. Therefore, the potential exclusion of some population groups- e.g. the elderly, people suffering from rare diseases, affected by disabilities or homeless should be carefully pondered when considering the adoption of specific digital health technologies; tech affordability, digital illiteracy or low digital literacy, shortage of internet connectivity and electricity are also core elements leading to an unequal access to digital health technologies across the region. Engaging local patient groups and members of local communities is important to understand local values, and needs, as well as assess whether the technologies can serve the interests of local communities. In order to address these challenges, a number of strategies can be identified, such as envisaging low-bandwidth designs, offline data capture, promoting inclusion pathways (through specific capacity-development initiatives) for women, the elderly and other particularly vulnerable people and considering context-specific tailored digital health interventions to avoid discrimination.

- **Care and respect for human dignity:** digital health technologies should only be applied when the dignity of the patient or research participant can be protected. On this ground, distant technologies (such as the use of telemedicine) should be avoided when disclosing news which put the patient or research participant in a vulnerable situation. In this context, preferable options should rely on personal and face-to-face communication, in order to protect the dignity of patients in particularly vulnerable conditions. Ensuring safety of the technology (in the sense that it does not cause harm to patients or research participants) is equally crucial, along with preserving the security of digital data generated from the use of digital health technologies. This data can be hacked by illegal scammers to blackmail and demand ransoms. Privacy and security issues should be addressed by relying on regular monitoring and evaluation of security systems. In this context, it is important to provide for legal remedies and compensation for privacy harms stemming from security breaches. In addition, mining large-scale data repositories requires adequate oversight mechanisms and data management: the representativeness of the datasets (avoiding biases in sample compositions) used for product development and the reliability of AI-driven analytic tools to mine such datasets can affect the development of effective digital health services and devices. Moreover, continuous or intermittent recording and transmission of detailed information about where people are and their regular habits through mobile health or wearable devices may breach privacy and confidentiality. Proportionate tracking is therefore recommended. In addition, epidemiology techniques using aggregate information (for instance from social media posts) for health purposes could give some indication about the diffusion of diseases, it also entails the risk of establishing a surveillance society through digital health. This use should be forbidden by law and tangibly avoided.

Respecting the dignity of patients or research participants means also considering possible forms of discomfort (being aware of which technologies can create uneasiness for patients or research participants, as it might be the case with wearable devices in some African contexts).

- **Trustworthiness:** clarity on how individuals and communities will benefit from digital health developments is a key aspect; oversight mechanisms protecting common interests and accountability mechanisms supporting public scrutiny is needed in this context. Different stakeholders raise new challenges regarding governance structures. Transparency should be fostered by identifying clear responsibilities and elaborating procedural values guiding governance for tech designers, providers and users. This is key to enhancing trust in SSA, where there is often reluctance towards clinical trials relying on digital health technologies due to fears of data exploitation. Hence, trustworthy digital health activities requires more than privacy protection: features of trust encompass meaningful human oversight, explainability when using AI tools, clarity regarding data ownership and data control.
- **Collaboration:** Health information and digital health solutions should be co-designed with local communities, in order to address health and digital literacy issues, as well as devise culturally-sensitive digital interventions to ensure acceptability and understanding of the technologies. A collaboration between ethicists, designers and developers of digital health technologies, that have a moral responsibility to design digital tools aligned with ethical forethoughts and aspects (for example, when designing algorithms for artificial intelligence, that represent all parts of the

population and leave no ground for bias and ensuing discrimination) should be fostered to promote an ethics-by-design approach.

- **Autonomy, informed consent and socio-cultural issues:** patients' choice to use digital health technologies must be voluntary and freedom not jeopardized by any sort of incentive (e.g. prioritization of patients that rely on digital tools, when they seek medical care in non-digital, conventional healthcare settings); a voluntary decision not to use digital health technologies must not be sanctioned or lead to a lack of access to health services. No undue inducement must be envisaged (for instance, accessing digital health care only to have smartphones, while underestimating the risks). Knowledge of the health workforce about digital technologies is often inadequate. Hence, appropriate technical training and education should be available, in order to understand the benefits and risks related to specific digital health interventions and reap the opportunities offered by these technologies. As digital health implementations rely on the specific context, people need tailored digital content in their own language, not only for access to healthcare systems but also for disease prevention or participation in clinical trials using digital tools. Nevertheless, SSA is dominated by a variety of languages and cultures resulting in cultural and contextual differences, which pose significant communication challenges: physicians or researchers are often required to translate complex technical terms and data-related concepts into local languages to facilitate informed consent processes. Ensuring translations that accurately grasp the intended meaning of data-related concepts is problematic, also because African language lexicons often do not have up-to-date translations for scientific terms. This challenge is exacerbated by the fact that many researchers lack vernacular linguistic competency, since they completed their science education in a foreign language. Engaging cultural mediators from local communities could help overcome communication barriers.

Furthermore, some ethical challenges pertain to the use of digital health technologies in clinical trials, notably in the context of decentralised trials. Considering these ethical issues will be of paramount importance to effectively support the STRATEGIC project's objective of strengthening the ethics and regulatory capacity in SSA and to ensure the design and deployment of responsible digital health technologies for clinical research and practice.

- **Shift from conventional clinical trials to decentralised clinical trials:** this could affect the quality of clinical trials and put data validity at risk; appropriate digital education is necessary. This might also affect the researcher-patient relationship, with the ensuing risk of dehumanizing trials, given the lack of face-to-face communication, and become challenging in African contexts where relationality is an important value.
- **Shift from a site-centric to a patient-centric approach:** participants have important responsibilities for data collection, outcome reporting. These activities were previously conducted onsite by the research teams and sometimes with the support of community health workers. This might become a challenge, particularly in settings with low literacy rates.

- **Ethical review and Compliance:** most NEC members have little or no experience in assessing clinical research protocols, including clinical trials, that involve digital health technologies. There is a clear need to strengthen capacity for reviewing research protocols with digital health components, ensuring that digital health concepts are well understood and that ethical and regulatory concerns can be properly recognized. Enhanced capacity is equally required for NRA members to develop guidelines that can effectively support and govern the review of digital health technologies

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List of tables

Country	Digital health technologies used in sub-Saharan Africa (clinical practice)
South Africa	The " MomConnect " project provides health information to expectant and new mothers via text messages.
Kenya	The "M- Tiba" program allows patients to pay for their health care via their mobile phones.
Uganda	The "Mobile VRS " (Virtual Reference Service) program offers remote medical consultations.
Tanzania	The " Wazazi program Nje Nje” uses SMS to provide health advice to expectant mothers and new parents.
Ghana	The "mPedigree", a phone-based system to face the issue of fake drugs: it is an innovative anti-counterfeit ICT software application that aims at empowering patients in areas with low literacy and low technical capacity via a free text message service to verify their medication’s safety; users can check the origin and authenticity of drug treatments before use.
South Sudan, Uganda, Tajikistan, Madagascar	A Digitized Care Management System was implemented by the World Food Program (WFP) and Famoco to provide healthcare assistance and monitoring within WFP nutrition programs.
Nigeria	"Lifebank", a mobile application that connects hospitals, doctors, blood banks, dispatch riders, to facilitate delivery of medical samples, oxygen and rare medicines.

Benin, Senegal, Ivory Coast	African Francophone Telemedicine Network (RAFT). Pan African e-Network Project.
Malawi	Drones are being used for delivery of blood and medical supplies from one clinic to another.

Table 1

Country	Digital health technologies used in sub-Saharan Africa (clinical trials)
Kenya	An open-source mobile digital platform for clinical trial data collection; trials on SMS messaging strategy to reduce neonatal mortality and to support maternally administered childhood mid-upper arm circumference monitoring and expand malnutrition screening.
South Africa, Kenya, Rwanda, Nigeria, Ethiopia, Malawi, Ghana, Sudan.	Research Electronic Data Capture (REDCap) Mobile Application: it allows research teams the option of using a non-internet-connected mobile device for field data collection, with synchronization to a “parent” REDCap database project whenever internet connectivity could be established.
Burkina Faso	A trial to reduce unnecessary caesarean deliveries, promoting the use of clinical algorithms for caesarean decision-making using in-site training, audits and feedback of caesarean indications and SMS reminders.
Tanzania	A trial involving text messages to increase attendance to follow-up cervical cancer screening appointments among HPV-positive women; a trial of AI-supported diabetic retinopathy screening.
South Africa	A trial of a mobile video entertainment-education intervention to promote exclusive breastfeeding; a trial involving mobile phone text messaging in promotion of breastfeeding among women living with HIV.
Uganda	A trial involving a mobile phone-based interactive voice response software on tuberculosis treatment outcomes; a trial involving a mobile application for improving adverse drug reaction reporting by healthcare professionals.
Ethiopia	A trial involving mobile phone based remote monitoring system for palliative care; a trial of mobile health on maternal health care service utilization; a trial of mobile phone text message reminders on improving completeness and timeliness of routine childhood vaccinations.

Rwanda	A trial involving mHealth-based integrated management of diabetes in primary healthcare; a trial of mobile health technology to identify and refer caesarean-related surgical site infections;
Guinea	A trial involving maternal deaths surveillance and response system at the health district level through digital communication tools.

Table 2